

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING THE DRILLING TECHNIQUES AND COLOR LETTER STORYBOARDING IN IMPROVING THE GRAMMAR SKILLS-AFFIXATION AMONG STUDENTS OF SPECIAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study is an action research on the use of drilling technique are applied in teaching and learning in the classroom. Students found to have the skills to spell but have difficulty in pronunciation of words involves affixation. The study involved a student in category learning disabilities under the Special Education Program Integration with Learning Disabilities (PPKIBP) at SMK Pulau Tawar, Jerantut, Pahang. This study was conducted within 2 months of 6 cycles. Observation, document analysis and interviews were used to collect data. Data was analyzed using content analysis and pattern analysis. Triangulation and time used to interpret the data revision process. Analysis of the data showed the drilling technique using coloured letter telling point positive impact in terms of improving the terms of remuneration on the basis of words and subsequently produce derivatives in teaching and student learning while improving the practice as a teacher and researcher.

Keywords: Drilling Techniques, colour letter storyboarding, students with learning disabilities, affixation

Introduction

The Reflection Of Experience Teacher in Teaching and Learning The study was conducted by the reflection of experience a teacher who teaches special education class at SMK Pulau Tawar, Jerantut, Pahang. Here's a little about the background of the teachers concerned.

Submissive Date : 1 Julai 2014
Graduation : Bachelor of Education (Special Education)
Honours
University : Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris (UPSI)
Practicum : SMK Pendeta Za'ba, Seremban, Negeri
Sembilan

Practicum Duration	:	6 months
Place of Duty	:	SMK Pulau Tawar, Jerantut, Pahang
Class Name	:	Kelas Pendidikan Khas (Anggerik)
Subject Taughts	:	Bahasa Melayu, Science, Education Islam, Physical Education, Science and Multimedia
Problems Identified	:	Most of the students can spell but cannot spell the words directly. Student mostly confused and had difficulty to spell the affixation consists of three letters as 'men', 'ter' and 'ber'. Student had difficulty to understand the passages of the text even the teacher read it together, always require repeated explanations by the teacher and also need assistance and instruction from the teacher during doing exercises.
Term Issues Identified:	:	Since January 2015

After implementing the teaching and learning of Malay Language, some difficulties are detected among students. Students facing to spell the affixation consists of three letters as 'men', 'ter' and 'ber'. This make students difficult to understand of text comprehension and face difficulties in completing the exercise given. Therefore, the explanation repeatedly during the teaching and learning as well as help the students and performing from the teacher always need to completing the consolidation exercise.

The Study Focus On

The implementation and observation of early detection test is done in two weeks. Students are asked to read the passages from the comprehension text using Buku Rampaian PBS Bahasa Malaysia (Berkemahiran, KSSR, Tahun 3A). During the first observation, student had been identified having difficulty in affixation spelling. Among the students who most obvious having difficulty is Nur Akmal Bin Adnan which identified slow down his voice, confused, always forget and spelling difficulty affixation in text comprehension. Figure 1 shows an example of a difficult affixation referred from the students: -

Unit 9
Badan Sihat Fikiran Cerdas

A Baca dan fahami petikan di bawah.

B2DBIEI

Yang mulia, Tuan Pengerusi Majlis, Yang Berusaha Puan Guru Besar Sekolah Kebangsaan Taman Permata Puan Zaleha binti Musa, barisan guru-guru penolong kanan, guru-guru dan rakan sekalian. Tajuk syarahan saya pada petikan ini ialah "Kebaikan Bersenam".

Hadirin,
Kita mestilah bersenam setiap hari. Ini kerana otak yang cerdas datang daripada badan yang cergas. Terdapat pelbagai cara bersenam seperti berjoging, bermain bola sepak, berenang dan senamrobik.

Antara kebaikan bersenam ialah kita dapat mengurangkan tekanan setelah bekerja atau belajar sepanjang hari. Dengan berbuat demikian, kita juga berasa gembira. Kebaikan yang kedua ialah kita dapat mengelak masalah negatif seperti menghisap rokok.

Justeru, marilah kita bersenam untuk kesihatan diri. Sekian sahaja syarahan saya, terima kasih.

B2DBIEI

Berusaha

Affixation

Be ru sahan

Problem Affixation Spelling

Figure 1 - Nur Akmal Bin Adnan Spelling (9 Februari 2015)

Students are required to spell the words of 'berusaha'. But mention only involve the alphabet "Be" only (alphabetically red). Students will slow down his voice and having difficulty to combining the voice to the next alphabet become a word.

The second observation was conducted to verify the difficulties faced by the students and the students found it difficult to mention more than 3 characters in affixation as in the first observation. Figure 2 shows an example of a difficulty student having during affixation spelling:

mengelak

Affixation

**men je nge je nge
nge lak
mengelak**

Problem Spelling Affixation

Figure 2 - Nur Akmal Bin Adnan Spelling (9 Februari 2015)

Based on Figure 1 and Figure 2, Nur Akmal Bin Adnan found it difficult to spell the affixation exceeding three alphabet and can read only kv. Therefore several improvements designed to enhance the level of affixation terms of Nur Akmal.

Objective

Improvement of teaching and learning activities using the drilling techniques and color letter storyboarding. Increasing the level of student mastery the affixation.

Study Issues

How does the method drilling help improving teaching and learning in the subjects of Malay Language in Special Education classes? What is the impact of drilling method in terms of increasing the level of affixation quoted text comprehension of Malay Language in Special Education classes?

Planning And Implementation Of Action Study

Action Planning

Read by Goodmen (1973), psycholinguistics process from the observation on a word in the text and thus forming the meaning of the observations made are said to be read. Also according from Haidi (2008), the problem appearing from the inability to interpret the symbols (letters / visual) to be translated as a paragraph or word was spoken between the problems that occur in reading. Other sources is immaturity on intellectual and emotional, have a low level of self-concept, have poor memory, difficulty speaking in speech, impaired in perception, lack of stimulation and unfocused. The study focuses on the problem of reading to erect its word that starts with the affixation.

In Malay Language, affixation or addition is in the base, thereby producing derivatives such as noun, verb, adjective, adverb and verb number. There are four types of adjustment in the prefix, suffix, and clamp inserts. Prefix is an adjustment that is in front of the base, located suffix at the end of the base, nor clamp clamp remuneration policy and the remuneration of said inserts are inserted in the middle of the word.

Thus, using the method of teaching strategies in drilling it allows delivery of a complex information in a student's ability. The information can also be submitted is the information need not be provided earlier. According to Hj Kamarudin. Husin (1988), drilling techniques is a repetition of facts which have been studied and aims to achieve a level of proficiency is in addition to ensure its immortality. It is the result of a combination of eclectic approach inductive and deductive. In teaching implementation is in accordance with abilities and capabilities of students. This eclectic approach, using methods of linguistics, oral (aural), natural and direct as well as several techniques such as problem solving, demonstrations, and question and answer drills.

This eclectic approach means teaching presented results from a combination of all or some of the characteristics of a method to the new method. The teaching approach is essential to help improve their spelling and reading skills among students. When teaching requires teachers to use a variety of approaches, the eclectic approach will be used. Understanding of the eclectic method is a good method is the application of the various systems and approaches. It also is an effort to unite the various approaches and also produce a good meeting results from the use of this approach. Merging a variety of methods to this one also was the beginning of a system that is both practical to implement.

Color letters storyboarding has also been used to illustrate to students the letters in the highlighted text to differentiate affixation contained in the word.

Thus, the techniques applied in drilling lesson in narrative form color letters storyboarding capable of increasing the level of mastery of the pronunciation of affixation among students.

Implementation Of The Study

Action research was conducted during the teaching and learning. Table 1 shows the action research undertaken: -

Table 1 - Implementation Schedule Action

N	Activity	Implementation Date
1	Implementing measures 1- activity 1 Discuss problems arising in actions 1	25 March 2015
2	Implementing measures 2- activity 2 Discuss problems arising in actions 2	1 April 2015
3	Implementing measures 3- activity 3 Discuss problems arising in actions 3	8 April 2015
4	Implementing measures 4- activity 4 Discuss problems arising in actions 4	15 April 2015
5	Implementing measures 5- activity 5 Discuss problems arising in actions 5	29 April 2015
6	Implementing measures 6- activity 6 Discuss problems arising in actions 6	6 May 2015

Figure 3 - Color Letter Storyboarding circulated in: -

Figure 3 explains that the text passages which should be read in accordance with the daily teaching plan that has been designed. Color letter storyboarding requires Nur Akmal Bin Adnan difficulties to make list of the words that spell. Read the whole text and identify the difficulty of each words when spelling and coloring activities initiated after reading the letter to identify the difficult during read a text with affixation.

Research Methodology

The study sample

A sample of these acts are students of with Learning Disabilities 'slow learner' categories. His name is Nur Akmal Bin Adnan, Malay and 17 years old. A student who is quiet, likes to ask and obey the instructions of the teachers.

Ethical Conducted During Action Studies

Applicants involve formal permission from the school authorities informing purpose, goals and methods used in the studies submitted to the Principal, Special Education Coordinator and teachers. Written permission from the sample measures also involve agreement on the right to privacy.

Methods of Collecting Data

Data in this action research using observation, interviews and document analysis. Do a thorough analysis of the evidence and support to issues and findings.

Observation

Observation was done in this study. Video footage was recorded Nur Akmal Bin Adnan activities while in class. Records show Nur Akmal made to sit on a nearby whiteboard on an equal footing, seems to focus on completing assignments and ask questions to complete the task.

Document analysis

Analysis of documents made from color letters storyboarding point that is used to view student achievement.

Interviews

Interview methods were used and questions posed were:

1. Can a students remember the words that were read?
2. Do you feel excited while reading?
3. Can the color letter storyboarding helps the student to remember the words that were read?

Data Analyzing Method

The method used in this study is the method of content analysis and pattern analysis. The information has been analyzed from the color letter storyboarding. The table was created to include the data from the point color letter storyboarding.

No	Aktivitiy	Implementation Date	Affixation Spelling	Problem In Affixation Spelling
1	Actions 1	25 Marh 2015	Berusaha	Spelling: Berusahan, Berusihan
2	Actions 2	1 April 2015	binti	Spelling: bin
3	Actions 3	8 April 2015	syarahan	Spelling: sarahan
4	Actions 4	15 April 2015	hadirin	Spelling: hadiran
5	Actions 5	29 April 2015	mestilah	Spelling: maktilah, mesti ah
6	Actions 6	6 May 2015	cerdas	Spelling: cergas

The results from the analysis, Nur Akmal Bin Adnan achievement is increasing. But when Nur Akmal absent from class, achievement in reading will decrease as forgetfulness and difficulty when spelling the word with affixation.

Actions 1

Actions 2

Actions 3

Actions 4

Actions 5

Actions 6

Methods Data Review

Triangulation source method and triangulation time methods currently used to support the subsequent data analysis used in this study.

The same training was given to the students for future triangulation time methods of Figure 1 and repeated in Figure 2. The difference of view will expand and strengthen knowledge opinion (Azman Wan Chik, 1989) and from this statement is the triangulation of teachers through discussion on the methods and the techniques used in the course of the study began from 25 March 2015. The following is a transcript of triangulation source methods of an interview with Mr Mohd Muhaimim on 6 May 2015, namely: -

- Mr Mohd Muhaimim : Drilling methods used to help students when reading. Especially during the students read the word with affixation. The drilling techniques combining with color letter storyboarding used to help students improve pronunciation and fluency when reading.
- Me : A good task
- Mr Mohd Muhaimim : Use of this method showed a positive effect for teaching in the classroom.
- Me : Suitable for the next class

Reflections Finding

This study requires an in-depth details to see the achievements of students in each class. The results observed during the teaching and learning involves students' work with the schedule set. Students performed more smoothly terms of reference in terms of remuneration and reduce errors. Offenses decreased in action 6. Students are also more fun, interesting and motivated while studying.

From this study, it was found that the color letter storyboarding used while teaching is to help provide a positive impact on teaching and learning in the classroom. In addition, it can motivate students to learn and make students more motivated during learning. According to Muhaiban Kassim (2003), materials to be used, to understand the background and the student environment is an aspect that should be considered when the process of learning and teaching is helped by the teaching planning.

Suggestions Upcoming Action Study

Action studies using the drilling and color letter storyboarding will be applied to all students in a class by using different studies and methods that have been used in this study. Qualitative and quantitative methods will be used to collect data for the next action study.

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